

LINGUISTICS AND PHILOLOGY

Suyunova Sevinch

Master student of University of Exact and Social Sciences

Abstract: The scientific study of language in all of its forms—not just one language, but all of the languages spoken around the world—is known as linguistics, or linguistics. The ancient Greek word φιλολογία, which means "love of words, " is where the word philology originates. Philology is the study of a people's culture as it manifests itself in their language and literary works. There are frequently disagreements on the identity of these concepts because philology and linguistics are closely related fields. Although both majors study languages and all things associated with them, the majority of experts concur that they differ greatly from one another. How do linguistics and philology vary from one another?

Key words: Philology, linguistics, profession, creativity, culture

The word "philology" comes from the ancient Greek φιλολογία - "love of the word." Philology studies the culture of a people, which is expressed in the language of that people and in its language literary creativity. Previously, the field of knowledge that studied literature and language, they called it verballity. Then the conversation broke off.

The names "linguistics" and "literary studies" came into use. Linguistics began to consider language as a system, while literary studies began to focus on the culture expressed through language and literary works. However, both fields are still united by a common name - philology. Scientific interests linguists focus on languages, while philologists study texts and literature, created in a certain language. However, a full study of the text also includes its linguistic analysis. In addition, it is also impossible to learn a language apart from of written culture; therefore, a linguist must be able to work with texts like a philologist.

A philologist, if he is not engaged in linguistics, must give an evaluative aspect to his scientific work. A literary scholar cannot and should not distance himself from personal perception, while a linguist must maintain neutrality and should not evaluate the object of research. For philologists, language is not only a system of symbols, but also a part of the literary and cultural heritage of its speakers. The activities of specialists in this field are based on their individual perception.

Philology encompasses a wider range of knowledge than linguistics. In this regard, it can be said that all linguists are philologists, but not all philologists are linguists. In the foreign education system, a linguist is usually called a specialist who studies the theory of language and its practical application, while a philologist is considered a researcher of fiction. His work with language is often limited to the analysis of individual expressive means². Despite all the differences, the field of activity of philologists and linguists is one - the study of language and all its aspects.

Philologist and linguist: what is the difference?

While linguistics is often considered a field of theoretical knowledge, it also includes a lot of practice. Linguists study language literally "by to the bricks, " studying its history, structure, comparing one language with another and delving into the depths of ancient and rare dialects. What is philology? The term originates from Greek and means "love of language." Philologists study a specific language, but they immerse themselves in it completely, paying great attention to literary works and cultural heritage written by native speakers. They also work on developing methods for teaching foreign and native languages in schools. In contrast, linguists approach language in a more detached and schematic manner³.

In the modern paradigm of humanities knowledge, two features distinguish philology: anthropocentrism and text centrism. The first relates philology to other humanities, asserting, "Scientific objects are primarily studied according to their role for humans, their purpose in human life activities, and their functions for the development and fulfillment of human personality." Philology has two functions: a

² Гращенко, 2017 Гращенко П.В. Композициональность в лексической и синтаксической деривации разноструктурных языков: Дис.д-р филол. наук. М. МГУ им. М.В. Ломоносова, 2017. стр: 55.

³ Исакадзе, Кобозева, Фундаментальные направления 1997. стр: 19.

broad universal one, which is connected to philology, and a narrow specialized one, which is related to linguistic and literary interpretation of artistic texts. These two functions in philology are interconnected and one cannot exist without the other. Philology as a science has a complex nature; the functions of philology determine its complex internal structure. The internal structure consists of general disciplines and specialized auxiliary ones.

Traditionally, philology is understood as a combination of two disciplines: linguistics and literary studies. There are also many specialized disciplines related to philology, such as paleography, hermeneutics, textology, linguistic text theory, discourse theory, poetics, rhetoric, speech culture, and others.

Philology is a complex field of humanistic knowledge, with text as its main object of study. This is because philology serves as a means of understanding and self-discovery of the spiritual culture of different peoples through their linguistic, written, and artistic literature. This makes philology an important element of the modern anthropocentric humanistic paradigm.

At the same time, philologists study a wider range of areas in human life, including history, sociology, cultural studies, and especially literature, because language penetrates into the emotional sphere of a person. To a certain degree, any linguist can be referred to as a philologist, however not all philologists will view language as dry and schematic as linguists do. We are first discussing methods for learning languages. Because its primary goal is extensive investigation, linguistics is more akin to a technical science. At its core, philology is a human science. He defends the traditional literary language, extolling its richness and diversity, and it is based on an intuitive understanding of the universe⁴.

It is evident that Russian linguists take the phenomena of foreign borrowings in the Russian language extremely seriously and are calm about it, whereas other philologists view it as a national disaster.

To put it another way, the primary distinction between a linguist and a philologist is that the former views the latter as an outside expert and uses the former

⁴ Лютикова синтаксис именной группы в безартиклевом языке: 2017, стр:43.

as an object of study. He studies the second language's growth in a literary direction, using it as a tool from within.

Professionals typically disregard these conditional limitations because linguists and philologists can operate in several disciplines. As a result, they frequently become teachers of Russian language and literature, foreign languages, journalists, editors, or translators⁵.

Any linguist can get employment in the field of "Philology, " but doing so requires professional retraining. Philologists can also find employment as philology teachers by passing the necessary courses. In the past, getting a second higher degree was required to enter a new job quickly with a much higher level of training and expertise. He suggests this viewpoint to anyone who wants to join the Modern Scientific and Technological Academy (SNTA)⁶.

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⁵ Лютикова Е.А. Формальные модели падежа: теории и приложения. М.2017. стр: 77.

⁶ Митренина О.В. Романова Е.Е., Слюсарь Н.А. Введение в генеративную грамматику. М.2012. стр: 98.